

CONGRATULATORY SPEECH ACT IN LITERARY TEXT

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Annotatsiya: Keyingi yillarda tilshunoslikda matn tahlili bilan bog'liq yangidan-yangi yo'nalishlar, sohalar shakllanmoqda. Bu holat, ayniqsa tilshunoslarning diqqat-e'tiborlarini matnga va uning lisoniy tabiatini o'rganishga ko'proq qaratayotganliklarida hamda olib borilayotgan tadqiqotlarning asosiy qismini badiiy matnlar tahlili tashkil etayotganligi ham seziladi. Maqolada muallif tomonidan ana shunday badiiy matnda tabrik nutqiy akti to'g'risida so'z yuritgan.

Kalit so'zlar: matn, badiiy matn, tabrik, muoamala.

Abstract: In recent years, new directions and fields related to text analysis are being formed in linguistics. This situation is especially noticeable when linguists pay more attention to the text and its linguistic nature, and the main part of the ongoing research is the analysis of literary texts. In the article, the author talked about the speech act of congratulation in such an artistic text.

Key words: text, artistic text, greeting, interaction.

The artistic text, as is known, is formed based on the requirements and patterns of the artistic style, therefore poetic, romantic, solemn forms of expression are widely used in it. The choice of words, the structure of sentences, the use of lexical-semantic, rhythmic-intonational units also come from the requirements of this style. Because the study of the linguistic features of the text allows to draw certain conclusions about the language of the artistic work chosen for a certain research and the individual style of the creator. Based on this, it can be concluded that the text and its characteristics are also interested in the field of pragmatics, methodology, psycholinguistics, ethics, aesthetics, which are related to linguistics to one degree or another, to the formation of text linguistics, which is a separate field of linguistics. created the ground. In recent years, along with other fields of linguistics, text research has reached a new level of development. Over the past period, researches have been carried out in Uzbek linguistics on the study of texts related to the text problem and task styles from different perspectives. When talking about the text, it should be noted that not only in Uzbek linguistics, but also in Turkic and Russian linguistics, there are different views on the essence and definition of the concept of text. At this point, there is a need to define the content of the concept of text.

What is text? In the "Annotated Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" created by the linguist scientist A. Hojiyev, the term text is defined as "Speech reflected through side-by-side letters, writing, in general, a fragment of speech; text" is defined.

The linguist scientist M. Hakimov, who made observations on the study of pragmatic and syntagmatic features of Uzbek scientific texts, tried to clarify the essence of the concept of text in his observations. In his scientific research, he defines it as follows: "...Speech is expressed as an event related to the speech process of the speaker, and the text (text) is also a written (" written form of this speech event) ") is a fragment... "Speech" in its written form is equivalent to the term "text"... The written form of any speech expresses the essence of the concept of text... Text is oral speech, stabilized

relative to the context, certain rules and laws, and literary language written speech formed on the basis of the norms... The text is a means of communication between people not at the same time, but several centuries before and after." Naturally, research conducted within the framework of linguo-pragmatics is conducted on the basis of literary texts. When comparing the literary text with other texts that are characteristic of different forms of speech, its specific features as an artistic-aesthetic phenomenon are clearly visible. "It's no secret that an artistic text as an artistic-aesthetic whole is a complex, multi-layered phenomenon. Understanding the main idea - thought - content expressed in an artistic text is not only a difficult and complex creative process. It is spiritual-cultural, mental-emotional, and linguistic to understand the meaning of the completely unique, sometimes open, sometimes hidden, various signs, connotations, and half-cups at the bottom of the cup. possible as a result of aesthetic activity. In order to understand the content of any text, it is necessary and sufficient to know the lexicon and grammar of the language, in order to understand the content of the artistic text, it is also necessary to know the specific linguistic and poetic laws of the artistic text. In order to determine these laws, it is necessary to carefully analyze artistic texts.

In the literary text, there are many linguistic tools that increase the effectiveness of speech in the performance of the congratulatory speech act. Such texts express a number of meanings, such as desire, purpose, reason, and have illocutionary verb participles expressed in the form of "want" and "wish" as well as units that form the semantics of a congratulatory sentence. The perlocutionary act in the speech act of congratulation expresses the speaker's desire to enter into a relationship with the person to whom the speech is addressed. The speaker's main goal in communicating is to convey his sincere wishes and desires to the listener. The scheme of this situation is shown as follows. It is illocutionary act of the speaker to express his thoughts in order to congratulate the addressed person. The result of this action is the awakening of certain emotions in the listener, that is, the appearance of perlocutionary action, which is the result of illocutionary action. In the past, the realization of such actions was also considered a sign of culture. "In addition to communication between people, the role of communication with objects in reality is also important in the formation of culture. It is known that language plays the role of a special link and intermediary in the relationship between a person and reality. Language reflects reality, and culture is an integral part of this reality. Reality itself can be called national, and this nationalism is reflected in the language as a result of a unique "seeing" of the world, its perception.

As in all types of speech acts, in the congratulatory speech act, the first goal of the speaker to engage in communication is in the form of a locutionary goal, and it is common to all speech acts. The characteristic of this goal is the firm formation of the desire to perform the speech act of congratulation in the speaker's mind, the specificity and strength of the desire ensures that this action occurs in a unique way. Accordingly, during the implementation of the congratulatory speech act, the speaker's tone of voice, pitch and tension level, and the features of attracting the person to whom the speech is addressed by verbal or non-verbal means are highlighted in different ways. The communicative goal of the speaker plays an important role in the process of speech communication. In literary texts, special attention is paid to the mutual understanding, level and mood of the participants of the speech in the performance of the congratulatory speech act. Because these moods definitely affect the participants during the congratulation. Therefore, it is characterized by the fact that the role of verbal and non-verbal means, which ensure the illocutionary force of speech by the speaker, is significantly significant. The structure of communication among the participants of the speech determines

the outcome of the congratulatory speech act. However, "Today in modern science there are more than a hundred concepts of "transaction". As a result, human behavior began to be understood and described differently: a) as social relations; b) as communication and interaction; c) as a spiritual connection of two or more individuals; d) as an activity.

In this sense, according to some considerations, the following can be recommended: "Communication is a complex process of the emergence and development of relationships between people and their needs in their life activities. is a collaborative strategy for information sharing, understanding, and perception." The object of this problem is the ideal spiritual reality. Here we are talking about the mental, emotional and voluntary emergence of human thinking and the process of realizing his spirituality. Its subject is the spiritual and moral side of people's behavior and activities, as well as the specific mental processes of a group of people working in various tasks. The implementation of the above-mentioned cooperative strategy, that is, the effective completion of the congratulatory speech act, depends on the ability of the speaker to choose language units and the emergence of a certain attitude towards the thoughts expressed in the person to whom the speech is directed.

In order to ensure the illocutionary force of the speech act of congratulation, the speaker brings his thoughts into one system, not only relies on linguistic means, but also uses non-verbal means instead. In this case, the speaker tries to coordinate his speech with the pragmatic conditions and situation while performing the congratulatory speech act. When conveying the speaker's thoughts to the listener, the order of words and the structure of the sentence appear quickly in accordance with the speech situation. Linguist scientist M. Hakimov, thinking about the role of the speech situation in the realization of speech expressions, writes: "Participants of any discourse enter into a relationship using the opportunities given to them. The level of his authority in speech begins to be felt in that situation as well as in behavior. Such expressions are performative. In the expression of action, the social, communicative situation has its own statement in the full sense, and the activities of the speaker and the listener are also connected with that situation.

Let's turn to the following text taken from the story "Hotamtoy" by Olmas Umarbekov:

The old lady turned back. The boot was bigger and floppier. But still fresh, hot. He spent half of the winter in thin summer shoes and calishes. Now he wears the boots comfortably, it is enough to put a little cotton on the ends, they don't slip. As for the coat, it's as if it was poured. On top of that, neither thick nor thin. The same coat worn in Tashkent winters. Two yards away from home, his friend Zulayho's sister shouted through the iron gates:

- *Holposhshapa! Let Moro be!*

- *Thank you! - said Kholposha, his mouth reaching his ear. The next day he went to school wearing his new clothes. But no one in his class congratulated him or paid attention. Only the mother tongue teacher praised her coat among the clothes hanging by the blackboard:*

"Whose is this?" It's beautiful! Then for three or four girls:

- *Aunt Kholposhsha's! they said.*

- *Let him. Worn out, girl! said the teacher.*

In the above-mentioned text, the fact that Kholposhsha's friend Zulayho met his sister, wearing a new coat, was the reason for congratulation. In this place, the tradition that has become a habit among our people - a wish - congratulations to people who have a new item is reflected. In the next place, it can be seen that the congratulatory act expressed in the teacher's speech is mixed with the congratulatory act of desire. "The artistic text is an extremely complex

whole that expresses the content of the artistic work, is functionally complete, is formed on the basis of the image capabilities of the language, can freely combine various styles at the discretion of the author, and has the ability to give people aesthetic pleasure. . In the literary text, as in the texts of other styles, laws such as strict logic, simplicity, comprehensibility, normativity are not fully followed. It effectively uses artistic image tools. Effectiveness comes to the fore. Melodic, catchy words are often used. A harmonious music, an inner harmony can be felt in the depicted reality. It embodies many possibilities, such as making a person feel emotional, crying, laughing, leading to the world of fantasy, immersing in thoughts, forming aesthetic thinking, teaching to look at events from a deep, different perspective. The artistic text, as is known, is formed based on the requirements and patterns of the artistic style, therefore poetic, romantic, solemn forms of expression are widely used in it. The choice of words, the structure of sentences, the use of lexical-semantic, rhythmic-intonational units also come from the requirements of this style.

The example given above shows that the occurrence of the congratulatory speech act is closely related to the speech situation. they wish each other well. Such sentences are said when praying, congratulating on a relationship, saying goodbye, greeting, condolence. Their common feature is that such sentences have stabilized semantically and formally in the Uzbek language, most of them have become speech etiquette, and the content of positive wishes is understood from all of them. There are a number of places in this story where the speech act of congratulation is described. Above, we considered two situations in which the congratulatory speech act is expressed. The following scene took place in the circle of family members - parents:

Seeing his daughter in new clothes, her father had tears in his eyes.

"Mother, my daughter!" he said and hugged her and kissed her forehead.

- May you live long, be a big girl and wear a pair of such coats! - said his stepmother, patting him on the shoulder. - That's how I saw it, I held it tightly! Your father didn't bargain either, they gave him what he asked for. If I wasn't there, others would be caught!...

"Thank you," Kholposhsha said shyly and went to the stone window near the door and looked at herself. (O. Umarbekov "Hotamtoy")

In the cited text, the speech act of congratulation is combined with the act of caressing. In this case, the actions of the parents served to strengthen the content." The most important tool in the strengthening of caress is the tone, intonation and emphasis. The stronger the affection, the longer the chain of sentences with the meaning of caress.

According to our research, caressing is also manifested in paralinguistic means, that is, in body movements and facial expressions. For example, actions such as pinching or kissing the addressee's face, stroking the head, and hugging tightly to the bosom are included. In the process of expressing caress, a smile appears on a person's face." In all places where the speech act of congratulation is reflected in the work, the fact that people are not indifferent to the hero of the work, Kholposhsha, and their desire to share in her joy has its own artistic image.

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